

Studies in the Protective Action of Colloids. Part I. Ionic Adsorption in the Coagulation of Protected Sols.

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A review of the literature on the subject showed that very little quantitative information is available on the ionic adsorption by a sol when coagulated in presence of a protecting agent. The following experiments were carried out with colloidal arsenious sulphide protected by variously concentrated solutions of gelatine, sodium oleate, and starch, using solutions of ferric chloride, barium chloride and hydrochloric acid as coagulators.

EXPERIMENTAL.

By preliminary experiments, the range of the proper concentrations of the solutions of the protectors was determined, so that for these values, the coagulation of a given concentration of the sol due to any of the variously concentrated solutions of the electrolytes used was complete within at least 48 hours. The following procedure was adopted for measuring the ionic adsorption: 25 c.c. of the sol were taken into a number of 100 c.c. flasks which were previously well-cleaned, steamed and dried. In one of these flasks 25 c.c. of distilled water were added to the sol; in the rest, the same volume of the protector solutions of increasing concentrations were added. Then in every one of these, 50 c.c. of the electrolyte solution of a known concentration were carefully added, the mixture was once shaken, and allowed to stand for subsequent analysis. The concentration of the electrolyte was such as to produce complete coagulation in all the systems within the period mentioned above. The amount of ionic adsorption was measured by withdrawing a known volume from the clear supernatant layers of the flocculated sol.

The results in Tables I, II and III show the variation of the amount of ionic adsorption, when the concentration of the protector solution, *viz.*, gelatine, was varied. Coagulations were produced by different concentrations of barium chloride solutions. The amount of barium adsorbed by the coagulum was estimated as barium sulphate by the familiar gravimetric method. Blank experiments in which arsenious

sulphide was not added, showed that any inaccuracy involved due to incomplete precipitation of barium sulphate due to the presence of gelatine added, was of the order of 0.1 per cent.

a , denotes the original amount of barium present in the system before coagulation and is expressed as grams of BaSO_4 . The data under b , give the amount of the barium expressed in the same way after coagulation. The data under, $(a-b)$, denote therefore the amount of barium adsorbed by the coagulum. The data in the last column express $(a-b)$, as millimoles of barium. In the first column, under p , are given the percentage concentrations of the protecting solutions employed.

TABLE I.

Sol protected by gelatine

Conc. of the BaCl_2 solution = $N/20$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 4 g. of As_2O_3 per litre. $a = 0.3065$ g.

p .	b .	$a-b$.	Adsorption of Ba in m. mols.
0.0 %	0.2904	0.0161	0.0694
0.0031	0.2870	0.0195	0.0835
0.0062	0.2876	0.0189	0.0809
0.0125	0.2916	0.0149	0.0638
0.0250	0.2912	0.0153	0.0656
0.0500	0.2892	0.0173	0.0741
0.1000	0.2840	0.0225	0.0964
0.2000	Only partial coagulation.		

TABLE II.

Sol protected by gelatine.

Conc. of BaCl_2 solution = $N/20$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 2 g. of As_2O_3 per litre. $a = 0.2976$ g.

p .	b .	$a-b$.	Adsorption of Ba in m. mols.
0.0000	0.2888	0.0088	0.0377
0.0016	0.2864	0.0112	0.0480
0.0031	0.2966	0.0010	0.0043
0.0063	0.2904	0.0072	0.0308
0.0125	0.2936	0.0040	0.0171
0.0250	0.2852	0.0124	0.0531
0.0500	Much turbidity, but no settling.		
0.1000	Not much turbidity.		

TABLE III.

Sol protected by gelatine.

Conc. of BaCl_2 solution = $N/4$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 1.8 g. of As_2O_3 per litre. $a = 1.4560$ g.

p .	b .	$a - b$.	Adsorption of Ba in m. mols.
0.0000	1.4440	0.0120	0.0514
0.0012	1.4480	0.0080	0.0343
0.0025	1.4412	0.0148	0.0634
0.0050	1.4492	0.0068	0.0291
0.0100	1.4444	0.0116	0.0497
0.0200	1.4434	0.0126	0.0539
0.0300	1.4416	0.0144	0.0616
0.0400)			
0.0500 } Only partial coagulation.			
0.1000)			

The results in Tables IV, V, VI relate the amount of ionic adsorption at different concentrations of gelatine solution when ferric chloride was the coagulant. The amounts of the ferric ion adsorbed were estimated volumetrically by reduction with stannous chloride and titrating against standard dichromate solution. a , b , $(a - b)$ have their previous significance; they are expressed as c.c. of normal dichromate solution equivalent to the corresponding ferric chloride solutions.

TABLE IV.

Sol protected by gelatine.

Conc. of FeCl_3 solution employed = $N/1$. Conc. of the $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3 = 4$ g. of As_2O_3 per litre. $a = 102$ (0.5187 c.c.).

p .	b .	$a - b$.	Adsorption of Fe in m. mols.
0.000	53	49	25.41
0.015	52	50	25.94
0.031	53	49	25.41
0.062	52.5	49.5	25.67
0.125	52.25	49.75	25.81
0.250	53.25	48.75	25.31
0.500	51.75	50.25	26.10

TABLE V.

Sol protected by gelatine.

Conc. of FeCl_3 solution = $N/4$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 4 g. per litre. $a = 26.4$ (0.5187 c.c.).

p .	b .	$a - b$.	Adsorption of Fe in m. mols.
0.000	14	12.4	6.439
0.015	14	12.4	6.439
0.031	13.25	13.15	6.828
0.062	14.25	12.15	6.275
0.125	13.00	13.4	6.955
0.250	13.50	12.9	6.697
0.500	Incomplete coagulation.		

TABLE VI.

Sol protected by gelatine.

Conc. of the FeCl_3 solution = $N/4.5$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 4 g. per litre. $a = 44.96$ (0.2559 c.c.).

p .	b .	$a - b$.	Adsorption of Fe in m. mols.
0.000	20.45	24.51	6.270
0.005	20.20	24.76	6.345
0.010	20.25	24.71	6.333
0.020	20.40	24.56	6.295
0.025	20.90	24.06	6.141
0.050	20.50	24.46	6.269
0.100	20.15	24.81	6.350
0.140	19.70	25.26	6.474
0.200	Incomplete coagulation.		

The results in Tables VII and VIII show the variation of the ionic adsorption when barium chloride and hydrochloric acid respectively were used, with increasing concentrations of sodium oleate solutions. The adsorption of the barium ion was estimated as in the previous cases. Adsorption in coagulations with hydrochloric acid was estimated by titration with standard alkali solution. Due correction was applied in each case for the characteristic alkalinity of the sodium oleate solutions ; p , a , b , $(a - b)$ have their usual significance.

TABLE VII.

Sol protected by sodium oleate.

Conc. of the BaCl_2 solution = $N/2$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 4 g. of As_2O_3 per litre. $a = 2.9692$ g.

p .	b .	$a - b$.	Adsorption of Ba in m. mols.
0.000	2.9512	0.0180	0.077
0.003	2.9472	0.0220	0.095
0.006	2.9392	0.0300	0.129
0.012	2.9440	0.0252	0.108
0.015	2.9432	0.0260	0.111
0.018	2.9392	0.0300	0.129
0.024	2.9094	0.0598	0.159
0.030	2.9360	0.0332	0.142
0.037	2.9334	0.0358	0.153
0.045	2.9324	0.0368	0.158
0.060	2.9308	0.0384	0.165
0.075	2.9332	0.0360	0.154

In Table VIII, a denotes the original amount of the hydrochloric acid present in the system before coagulation, expressed as c.c. of standard alkali solution. b , $(a - b)$ are expressed in the same way as previously ; p denotes the percentage concentration of the protective agent solution employed. In this set, however, instead of keeping the volumes of the protecting solution and the coagulant, 25 c. c. and 50 c. c. respectively, they were reversed.

TABLE VIII.

Sol protected by sodium oleate.

Conc. of HCl solution employed = $N/10$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 4 g. of As_2O_3 per litre. $a = 152.3$ c. c.

<i>p.</i>	<i>b.</i>	<i>a - b.</i>	Adsorption of HCl in m. mols.
0.00	151.40 c. c.	0.90 c. c.	0.0686
0.05	150.09	2.20	0.1680
0.10	149.79	2.51	0.1915
0.20	149.54	2.76	0.2107
0.25	149.71	2.59	0.1973
0.30	148.16	4.14	0.3152
0.40	146.99	5.31	0.4106
0.50	146.62	5.68	0.4326

Table IX gives results for the barium ionic adsorptions when starch solutions were employed as protectors. The volumes of the sol, protector, and coagulant, were the same as in the first seven sets, *viz.*, 25 c.c., 25 c.c., 50 c.c. respectively.

TABLE IX.

Sol protected by starch.

Conc. of $BaCl_2$ solution employed = $N/2$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 6 g. of As_2O_3 per litre. $a = 2.9541$ g.

<i>p.</i>	<i>b.</i>	<i>a - b.</i>	Adsorption of Ba in m. mols.
0.00	2.8724	0.0817	0.350
0.02	2.8698	0.0843	0.361
0.04	2.8672	0.0869	0.372
0.06	2.8664	0.0877	0.376
0.07	2.8761	0.0780	0.384
0.08	2.8910	0.0631	0.270
0.09	2.8848	0.0693	0.297
0.10	2.8788	0.0753	0.323
0.11	2.8729	0.0812	0.348
0.12	2.8660	0.0881	0.378
0.14	2.8726	0.0815	0.349
0.16	2.8770	0.0771	0.330

Next, the adsorption of barium ions by the simple, unprotected arsenious sulphide sol at various dilutions was determined, and the results are given in Table X. Sols of various dilutions were obtained by diluting 1, 2½, 5 c. c. etc., of the stock sol to 25 c. c. Into each of these, 25 c. c. of barium chloride solutions were added, and the adsorption of barium ions was estimated after 24 hours. The data in the first column, denoted by *S*, indicate the number of c. c. of the stock As_2S_3 sol diluted to 25 c. c.

TABLE X.

No protector used

Conc. of BaCl_2 solution = $N/3$. Conc. of the As_2S_3 sol = 2 g. of As_2O_3 per litre, $a = 0.9946$ g.

<i>S</i> .	<i>b</i> .	<i>a</i> - <i>b</i> .	Adsorption of Ba in m. mols.
1 c. c. diluted to 25 c. c.	0.9882	0.0664	0.0274
2.5 "	0.9822	0.0124	0.0524
5 "	0.9846	0.0100	0.0428
7 "	0.9812	0.0134	0.0574
10 "	0.9776	0.0170	0.0728
12 "	0.9716	0.0230	0.0985
14 "	0.9680	0.0266	0.1140
16 "	0.9642	0.0304	0.1302
20 "	0.9622	0.0324	0.1388
25 "	0.9582	0.0364	0.1560

In Table XI are given the results of the variation of the ionic adsorption with the concentration of the protective agent solution, when the arsenious sulphide sol was not present in the system. In each case, 25 c. c. of barium chloride solution were added to 25 c. c. of sodium oleate solution of known strength. The estimation of the adsorption of barium ions after coagulation was done as usual. The data under, *p*, give the percentage concentrations of the sodium oleate employed.

TABLE XI.

*Adsorption by sodium oleate only.*Conc. of BaCl_2 solution = $N/3$. $a = 0.9936$ g.

p .	b .	$a - b$.	Adsorption of Ba in m. mols.
0.004	0.9852	0.0084	0.036
0.010	0.9824	0.0112	0.048
0.020	0.9752	0.0184	0.079
0.040	0.9646	0.0290	0.124
0.060	0.9520	0.0416	0.178
0.080	0.9592	0.0344	0.147
0.100	0.9556	0.0380	0.163
0.200	0.9518	0.0418	0.178
0.400	0.9168	0.0768	0.329

The curves in Figs. 1—3 relate the amount of ionic adsorption with that of the protecting agent in the system; these curves numbered 1, 2,11 correspond to data in Tables I, II, III,XI respectively.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

DISCUSSION.

The results show that in the majority of cases for small proportions of the protector, adsorption of the coagulator increases by increasing the amount of the protector. It is, however, interesting to see in a number of cases that an increase in the proportion of the protector has led to a diminution of ionic adsorption. This is particularly well brought out, *e. g.*, by the minimum in curve 9, Fig. 2, showing the variable adsorption of barium as the proportion of the starch, introduced initially as a protector, is increased progressively. In this connection it is interesting to refer to the results of Chowdhury and Das (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 378) on the decolorisation of oils by mixed adsorbents, *viz.* alumina and bauxite, silica and bauxite. They found that the amount of the colouring matter removed, plotted against the proportion of one of the constituents of the adsorbing mixture, yields a curve with maxima and minima similar to those observed in the present work. Work of Chowdhury and Pal (*ibid.*, 1930, 7, 451) on the adsorption of benzol vapour by mixed adsorbents shows similar results. We are of opinion that the discontinuities like the ones mentioned above and observed by us indicate the formation of adsorption complexes between the added protector and the original colloid, with characteristic adsorption capacities. Results observed when ferric chloride was used as a coagulator are interesting (*cf.* Tables IV, V, VI). It is seen that the amount of adsorption is practically constant although the proportion of the protector has been varied, *e. g.*, in Table IV from 0.015 to 0.5 per cent. It is also remarkable that the electrolytic adsorption of the sol when protected by gelatine is approximately the same as that for the unprotected sol.